

Metal-binding molecules in the organs of *Mus musculus* by size-exclusion chromatography coupled with UV spectroscopy and ICP-MS

M. González-Fernández¹, T. García-Barrera^{1*}, A. Arias-Borrego¹, D. Bonilla-Valverde², J. López-Barea², C. Pueyo², J. L. Gómez-Ariza¹

¹Departamento de Química y Ciencia de los Materiales, Facultad de Ciencias Experimentales, Campus de El Carmen, Avda. de Fuerzas Armadas S/N, 21007 Huelva, Spain

²Departamento de Bioquímica y Biología Molecular, Campus Universitario de Rabanales, Edificio Severo Ochoa (C-6), 2ª planta, Ctra. Madrid-Cádiz, Km 396a, 14071 Córdoba, Spain

*corresponding author: e-mail: tamara.garcia@dqcm.uhu.es

Abstract *Mus musculus* mice have been investigated for the total elements content in different organs (lung, liver, spleen, kidney, brain, testicle, heart and muscle) and molecular mass distribution patterns of Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Pb, Cr, Fe, Co, Se and Cd. Some differences have been found in the organs studied, with especially relevant being the Cu-containing fraction present only in the brain and the As-containing one in the liver. Other differences related to the abundance of the metallopecies have also been found. The present paper is the first step in the study of the “metallome” of this inbred laboratory species from which the genome is completely known. This organism could be used as a model in future studies focused on wild mice and

the analytical approach developed could be applied to wild mice to find markers of environmental pollution.

Keywords *Mus musculus* · Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry · Metallomics · Metals · Size-exclusion chromatography

Introduction

Mus musculus mice are classic inbred laboratory species and a great number of proteomic [1–4] and genomic [5–7] studies have been related to them, with the genome being completely known. In addition, studies developed with *Mus musculus* are not affected by differences related to the age, sex and living conditions, which are difficult to control with wild mice. For this reason *Mus musculus* can be used as a model organism for comparison with wild mice, such as *Mus spretus*. This latter species can be used as a key organism in pollution monitoring and environmental conservation [8] and in this sense, biochemical biomarkers have been measured in wild mice (*Mus spretus*) from Doñana National Park (UNESCO Reserve of the Biosphere, Ramsar Site and World Heritage Site north of Guadalquivir river estuary in Huelva, southwest Spain) [9, 10].

The increasingly relevant information related to genomes, gene transcripts, proteins and their functions, as well as their global and comprehensive analysis, often referred to as genomics and proteomics, is a fundamental contribution of analytical chemistry to the progress of research in life sciences [11–15]. Metals play an important role in the development and function of living organisms since the function of many proteins, referred as metalloproteins, critically depends on

The present paper is the first step in the study of the “metallome” of the inbred laboratory species *Mus musculus* from which the genome is completely known. Some interesting differences have been found in the extracts from the organs that are discussed in the text.

M. González-Fernández · T. García-Barrera (

A. Arias-Borrego · J. L. Gómez-Ariza
Departamento de Química y Ciencia de los Materiales,
Facultad de Ciencias Experimentales, Campus de El Carmen,
Avda. de Fuerzas Armadas S/N,
21007 Huelva, Spain

D. Bonilla-Valverde · J. López-Barea · C. Pueyo
Departamento de Bioquímica y Biología Molecular,
Campus Universitario de Rabanales, Edificio Severo Ochoa (C-6),
2ª planta, Ctra. Madrid-Cádiz, Km 396a,
14071 Córdoba, Spain

their interaction with metals, usually transition ones, such as Cu, Fe, Zn or Mo. Some proteins, as in the case of metallothioneins, are involved in a defense mechanism of the organisms against heavy-metal stress, while others are transporters of essential nutrient ions, contaminants and metal probes [11]. The understanding of these protein processes requires not only the identification of molecules involved and characterization of their complexes with metals but also the characterization of the pool of all nonproteinaceous molecules, with a relatively small size, some of which deliver metals to metalloproteins [16]. In spite of molecular mass spectrometry (MS) being a powerful analytical tool for this purpose, the results provided are unable to get the complete information required. In connection with this, the information on metal–protein interactions is usually lost in the gas phase when matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization (MALDI) is used, or is not acquired because of insufficient detection limits in real-world salt-rich samples when electrospray ionization (ESI) is applied. However, the plasma source plays an important role in bioanalytical chemistry in general and in proteomics in particular [17–19]. Inductively coupled plasma (ICP) MS presents numerous advantages, like isotope specificity, versatility and high sensitivity, down to subfemtogram levels. In addition, ICP-MS becomes a molecule-specific technique when applied as a detection system in chromatography or electrophoresis [20], which is a key advantage for this technique. The sequential use of size-exclusion chromatography (SEC), ion-exchange high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and/or capillary electrophoresis (CE) allows the separation of individual metallospecies prior to their detection by ICP-MS. On the other hand, the combination of UV spectroscopy and ICP-MS makes possible the detection of elements and biomolecules at the same time. In this sense, Mn compounds have been determined by CE coupled with ICP-MS in liver [21] and human milk by SEC–anion exchange–ICP-MS [22]. Selenium speciation has been carried out in nuts by HPLC coupled with ICP-MS [23] and ESI-MS [24] and also in yeast by means of SEC-CE-ICP-MS [25], SEC- HPLC-ICP-MS and MALDI–time-of-flight MS [26]. In addition, the fractionation of Ni, Cu, Zn, and Mn in nuts [27, 28] and soybean flour by SEC-ICP-MS [29] has been performed. Multielemental fractionation studies have also been performed by SEC-ICP-MS in premature human milk [22, 30] and whey milk [31].

In the present work, a number of metallospecies from several organs of *Mus musculus* mice, namely, lung, liver, spleen, kidney, brain, testicle, heart and muscle, were extracted and analyzed by SEC-UV-ICP-MS. The molecular mass distribution patterns of elements in each organ are discussed and some important differences are found between them. The total contents of the most important heavy metals and other toxicologically relevant elements

(Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Pb, Cr, Fe, Co, Se and Cd) were estimated by ICP-MS. The total content of proteins was also determined by the Bradford method.

Experimental

Standard solutions and reagents

For total elements determination, standard solutions were prepared by dilution of a multielement standard (1000 mg l⁻¹ in 1 M HNO₃) obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Nitric acid (65%), hydrochloric acid (37%), perchloric acid (70–72%) and hydrogen peroxide (30%) of Suprapur® grade (Merck) were used for the mineralization of the samples. A solution containing Li, Y, Tl and Ce (10 µg l⁻¹ each) in 2% nitric acid (Agilent Technologies, USA) was used to tune the ICP-MS instrument with regard to the sensitivity, resolution, percentage of oxides and doubly charged ions. The mobile phase solution was prepared daily as 0.05 M tris (hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (Tris), pH 8.0 from Trizma base and Trizma hydrochloride (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany).

A solution containing 0.002 M ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid disodium salt dihydrate (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) was used to clean the SEC columns. Dithiothreitol (DTT), phenylmethanesulfonyl fluoride (PMSF), protease inhibitors and benzonase were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). The dye reagent concentrate for the protein assay was supplied by Bio-Rad (Munich, Germany). The molecular mass calibration standards (bovine serum albumin, metallothionein I, gastrin rat I, Gly6, chymotrypsinogen A, ribonuclease A, metallothionein I and blue dextran) for the SEC columns were supplied by Amersham Biosciences (Uppsala, Sweden). Ultrapure water (18 MΩ cm) from a Milli-Q gradient system (Millipore, Watford, UK) was used throughout.

Instrumentation

A MARS microwave-accelerated reaction system (CEM, Matthews, NC, USA) was used for the mineralization of the samples. Semipreparative SEC was carried out in both a Hiloal 26/60 Superdex 30 Prep column for a separation range below 10 kDa (low molecular mass, LMM) and a Superdex 75 Prep column for a separation range of 3–70 kDa (high molecular mass, HMM), both from Amersham Biosciences (Uppsala, Sweden). An AKTA-Prime system (pump and UV detector at 254 nm) (Amersham) was used as the eluant delivery system, equipped with a 500-µl sample loop.

Elemental detection was performed using a model 4500 ICP-MS instrument (Hewlett-Packard, USA). A model 5804 R

centrifuge (Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany) was used to accelerate the phase-separation process in the extraction of the compounds.

Procedures

Animals and sample preparation

Mus musculus (inbred BALB/c strain) mice were from Charles River Laboratory (Spain). Mice of 7 weeks of age were fed ad libitum with feed conventional pellets. This feed contained 11.9% moisture, 16.1% crude protein, 3.1% crude oil, 60% N-free extract (including starch, sugars, crude fiber, etc.) and 5.1% total minerals. Element concentrations included in the feed were as follows (the limits recommended for each of these elements are indicated in parentheses): 70 mg kg⁻¹ Mn (40–100 mg kg⁻¹), 17 mg kg⁻¹ Cu (10–35 mg kg⁻¹), 200 µg kg⁻¹ Pb (less than 1,500 µg kg⁻¹), 21 µg kg⁻¹ Hg (less than 100 µg kg⁻¹), 70 µg kg⁻¹ As (less than 1,000 µg kg⁻¹), 51 µg kg⁻¹ Cd (less than 250 µg kg⁻¹), 160 µg kg⁻¹ Se (less than 600 µg kg⁻¹).

Mice were individually killed by cervical dislocation and dissected. Individual organs were excised, weighed in Eppendorf vials, cleaned with 0.9% NaCl solution, frozen in liquid N₂ and stored at -80 °C until they were used for extract preparation. Mice were handled according to the norms stipulated by the European Community. The investigation was performed after approval by the Ethical Committee of the University of Córdoba (Spain).

Entire organs of each type (lungs, livers, spleens, kidneys, brains, testicles, hearts and muscles) from 20 different animals were pooled. The weights of the organs in the pool were as follows: 3.444 g (lungs), 1.757 g (livers), 7.462 g (spleens), 7.313 g (kidneys), 3.265 g (brains), 2.901 g (testicles), 9.565 g (hearts) and 9.565 g (muscles). After that a solution (3 ml g⁻¹) was added containing the following: 50 mM Tris-HCl buffer solution at pH 8, 1 mM DTT, 1 mM PMSF and protease inhibitors (100 µl ml⁻¹). Later, benzonase was added (500 U ml⁻¹) to the extracts, they were incubated for 30 min at room temperature and, finally, were centrifuged at 80,000 rpm for 1 h. Extracts were stored at -80 °C until analysis.

Total elements determination

Mineralization of the extracts from the different organs was carried out in a microwave-accelerated reaction system. For this purpose, the extracts were weighed exactly (0.5000 g) in 55-ml microwave vessels and 10 ml of a mixture containing nitric acid and hydrogen peroxide (4:1 v/v) was added. After 10 min, the PTFE vessels were closed and introduced into the microwave oven. The mineralization was carried out at 1,200 W from room temperature ramped to 180 °C in 15 min and with holding for 40 min at this temperature. After that

solutions were made up to 25 ml and analyzed by ICP-MS. Finally, Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Pb, Cr, Fe, Co, Se and Cd were measured in the extracts from the different organs.

Total proteins content

The total content of proteins was determined in the extracts following the standard Bio-Rad protein assay. Briefly, the commercial dye reagent (dye, phosphoric acid and methanol) was fivefold diluted with Milli-Q water and was used to make the standard and sample solutions. A calibration curve was prepared with bovine serum albumin from 200 to 1,400 mg l⁻¹. An 50-µl aliquot of the extracts was diluted to 10 ml with the diluted dye reagent. In some cases, the samples were additionally diluted so as to be in the range of the calibration curve constructed. Absorption was measured at 595 nm against a blank solution.

Analysis of extracts by SEC coupled with UV spectroscopy and ICP-MS

First of all, the extracts were diluted twofold with the mobile phase, centrifuged at 110,000 rpm for 1 h at 4 °C and passed through Iso-Disc poly(vinylidene difluoride) filters (25-mm diameter, 0.2-µm pore size) to avoid column overloading or clogging.

Elemental fractionation profiles of the extracts from the different organs were obtained by SEC using the two columns described in "Instrumentation." Elemental detection was carried out using UV and ICP-MS detectors. The SEC-UV-ICP-MS on-line coupling was performed by connecting the outlet of the UV detector to the nebulizer inlet of the ICP-MS instrument. The tuning of the ICP-MS instrument was performed by adding Li, Y, Ce and Tl (10 µg l⁻¹ each) to the mobile phase (0.05 M of Tris-HCl at pH 8.0) and using the AKTA-Prime system as a delivery system (2 ml min⁻¹). However, the mobile phase was not passed through the columns since retention of Y was observed. The instrumental operating conditions are given in Table 1.

Quality control of the SEC-UV-ICP-MS analysis

The quality control of the analysis was demonstrated to be important to overcome problems related to contamination, loss and stability of the species as previously described [28]. Briefly, it consisted of several considerations:

1. Extensive care was taken in relation to the use of metal pieces and they were substituted by plastic spatulas, injection syringes and so on.
2. The possible retention of elements and molecules after each run was tested during one-half column volume monitoring the signal in the UV detector and the ICP-MS

Table 1 Instrumental conditions for size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) and inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS)

Instrumental operating conditions	
SEC conditions	
Columns	Hiload 26/60 Superdex 30 Prep Hiload 26/60 Superdex 75 Prep
Resolution range	$M_r < 10,000$ Da; 3,000–70,000 Da
Mobile phase	50 mmol l ⁻¹ tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (pH 8.0)
Flow rate	2 ml min ⁻¹
Injection volume	500 μ l
UV-vis wavelength	254 nm
ICP-MS conditions	
Forward power	1,266 W
Plasma gas flow rate	15.8 l min ⁻¹
Auxiliary gas flow rate	1.07 l min ⁻¹
Carrier gas flow rate	0.9 l min ⁻¹
Sampling depth	5.8 mm
Sampling and skimmer cones	Platinum
Dwell time	0.3 s per isotope
Isotopes monitored	⁵⁵ Mn, ⁶⁰ Ni, ⁶³ Cu, ⁶⁶ Zn, ⁷⁵ As, ²⁰⁸ Pb, ⁵³ Cr, ⁵⁷ Fe, ⁵⁹ Co, ⁸² Se, ¹¹¹ Cd

instrument. The possible elements retained on the SEC columns were eliminated by passing one column volume of 0.002 M EDTA solution. In the same way, to eliminate most proteins nonspecifically adsorbed to the stationary phase one column volume of 0.5 M NaOH was passed. After being cleaned, the columns were equilibrated with at least three column volumes of mobile phase until the UV baseline stabilized before the next sample was applied.

Molecular mass calibration of the size-exclusion columns

In order to determine the molecular masses of the compounds present in the UV and ICP-MS chromatograms from the extracts analyzed by SEC-UV-ICP-MS, calibration curves were constructed using standards of known molecular mass. For the LMM column, the calibration standards were bovine serum albumin (67,000 Da), metallothionein I (7,000 Da),

gastrin rat I (2,126 Da) and Gly6 (360 Da). For the HMM column, the calibration standards were bovine serum albumin (67,000 Da), chymotrypsinogen A (25,000 Da), ribonuclease A (13,700 Da) and metallothionein I (7,000 Da). The relation between the retention time (determined by the peak maxima in UV detection) and the molecular mass (daltons) for both columns is shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The void retention time was determined in the LMM and HMM columns using bovine serum albumin (67 kDa) and blue dextran (2,000 kDa), respectively.

Results and discussion

Optimization for the total elements determination and final results

Two digestion procedures were tested for the analysis of total elements in the extracts obtained from the organs. One of them was based on a wet digestion in open PTFE vessels with 15 ml of a HNO₃/HCl mixture (3:1, v/v) and 5 ml of HClO₄ for 12 h. Afterwards, the PTFE vessels were placed in a heated sand bath until dryness had been achieved, and then the addition of acids was repeated, but now under heating. The recoveries for the elements determined were in the range 85–112% for all the elements, except for As (56%), and the relative standard deviations ($n=3$) were from 5 to 8%; however, this procedure is time-consuming (about 24 h per sample).

The second one was based on the use of a microwave-accelerated reaction system. This procedure provides recoveries in the range 79–110%, except for Se (64%), with relative standard deviations ($n=8$) from 5 to 10%. The procedure has a high throughput (1 h per sample) and provides good recoveries and relative standard deviations and for this reason it was selected for further studies.

The recovery experiments were carried out by measuring the concentration of the elements in the extracts before and after a 40 μ g l⁻¹ spike. Calibration curves were constructed

Fig. 1 Molecular mass calibration curve for the Hiload 26/60 Superdex 30 Prep column. T_r retention time

Fig. 2 Molecular mass calibration curve for the Hiload 26/60 Superdex 75 Prep column

by plotting the instrumental signal against the concentration of the standards. The limits of detection were defined as $(a + 3S_y/x)$ and limits of quantification were defined as $(a + 10S_y/x)$, where a is the ordinate intercept and S_y/x is the random errors in the values for the slope and the intercept. After reshaping of the calibration function, we obtained the concentration at the detection limit or the quantification limit by substituting the values given above. Instrumental detection limits and recoveries are given in Table 2 along with the concentrations of the elements in the extracts.

As can be inferred from Table 2, As and Cd were under the instrumental detection limits in all the extracts analyzed. Cobalt was detected only in the lung extract and Fe was not found in brain and testicle.

Total protein content in the extracts

The highest concentration of proteins was found in the extract of liver and the lowest was found in that of brain. The total protein contents of the different extracts of the organs are as follows: 13 mg ml⁻¹ (lung), 34 mg ml⁻¹ (liver), 22 mg ml⁻¹ (spleen), 31 mg ml⁻¹ (kidney), 2.1 mg ml⁻¹ (brain), 10 mg ml⁻¹ (testicle), 10 mg ml⁻¹ (heart) and 23 mg ml⁻¹ (muscle).

Profiles obtained by SEC and UV detection

The UV detector, as described earlier, was used first for the introduction of the eluate from the SEC columns into the ICP-MS instrument. The wavelength selected was 254 nm since it allows good response. The superimposed UV chromatographic profiles of the extracts from the different organs are shown in Fig. 3a.

The combined use of both columns allowed a good separation of compounds in the range 360–70,000 Da. As can be seen in Fig. 3, all the samples showed a high-intensity peak in the void volume of the LMM column (more than 10 kDa, determined with bovine serum albumin) that is within the molecular mass separation range of the HMM column. In addition, chromatographic peaks were absent in the void volume of the HMM column (70 kDa, determined with blue dextran).

Molecular size distribution UV profiles with the LMM column (below 10 kDa)

As shown in Fig. 3a, all the samples studied have several peaks in the region of the lowest molecular mass referred to in the figure as Gly6 (360 Da), which represent the standard injected and its molecular mass in parentheses. In this region, all the samples, except those corresponding to extracts from liver and lung, have one high-intensity peak in this region corresponding to elution at the same retention time. The UV chromatographic profiles of the extracts from liver and lung are different from each other and from those of the other samples, as previously commented on. In this molecular mass region, the UV chromatographic profiles of kidney and testicle are similar to each other but are different from those of the other samples, showing two high-intensity peaks.

In the next molecular mass region, from 360 to 2,126 Da, most of the samples have several peaks that are not clearly resolved. However, the high-intensity chromatographic peak detected in the spleen extract is distinctive.

Table 2 Concentration of elements ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$) in the extracts of the different organs of the mice

	Cr	Mn	Fe	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	As	Se	Cd	Pb
Spleen	227±4	58.1±20.5	8,103±2,368	ND	208.9±62.2	346±382	1,017±434	ND	ND	ND	14.3±4.0
Brain	357±37	105.5±1.3	ND	ND	167.2±3.3	727±164	3,016±1880	ND	48±13	ND	14.9±5.3
Heart	213±32	70.8±13.7	5,104±492	ND	122.9±2.5	153±4	794±471	ND	58±4	ND	15.1±1.6
Liver	482±23	216.5±45.9	6,085±604	ND	284.5±0.1	1927±667	4,369±166	ND	289±9	ND	32.5±20.1
Muscle	473±29	98.2±2.4	5,792±795	ND	193.9±0.1	108±22	1,400±895	ND	49±21	ND	45.6±25.9
Lung	504±40	542.4±43.9	5,427±504	32.8±1.2	137.2±4.2	593±21	3,818±443	ND	233±13	ND	41.8±1.1
Kidney	518±20	103.1±12.3	14,744±674	ND	75.3±5.5	304±15	1,596±275	ND	150±18	ND	24.2±1.3
Testicle	445±61	92.9±3.2	ND	ND	139.6±2.8	286±25	2,846±817	ND	194±34	ND	25.3±2.3
LOD ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$)	2	2	6	0.8	1	5	3	2	4	5	0.8
Recovery (%)	98	106	101	110	104	92	85	79	64	82	95

Average of three replicates ($n=3$)

LOD limit of detection, ND not detected

Fig. 3 a Superimposed low molecular mass (LMM) UV chromatographic profiles and b superimposed high molecular mass (HMW) UV chromatographic profiles of the extracts from the organs studied. BSA bovine serum albumin, MT metallothionein

Between the last molecular mass region mentioned and the void volume of the SEC column, all the chromatograms show an absence of peaks.

Molecular size distribution UV profiles with the HMM column (3–70 kDa)

Figure 3b shows the UV chromatographic profiles of the samples analyzed by using the HMM SEC column. It is important to point out that the chromatographic peaks corresponding to elution in the void volume of the LMM column are detected within the molecular mass separation range of the HMM SEC column. These molecules are in the molecular mass range from 25 to 67 kDa for all the samples

analyzed. As in the case of the LMM column, a lot of chromatographic peaks are detected.

For all the samples analyzed, the chromatographic profiles obtained in the lowest molecular mass range of this column are similar to those obtained with the LMM column in its lowest molecular mass separation range. This fact leads us to conclude that these chromatographic peaks correspond to molecules with molecular masses below 3 kDa and near to 360 kDa.

Molecular size distribution patterns of elements by SEC-ICP-MS

To obtain the SEC-ICP-MS profiles, Mn, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Pb, Cr, Fe, Co, Se and Cd were measured. However, Cr,

Fig. 4 Molecular size distribution patterns of Cu obtained by size-exclusion chromatography-inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (SEC-ICP-MS) with a the LMM column and b the HMM column. Numbers correspond to the standards of known molecular mass: 1 67 kDa, 2 25 kDa, 3 13.7 kDa, 4 7 kDa and 5 less than 3 kDa

Cd, Co and Se were not detected in any sample or the intensity was very low and with high noise.

Some differences were found in the extracts from the organs in relation to the chromatographic profiles of elements obtained with the SEC columns coupled to the ICP-MS instrument. These results are discussed in detail in the following text.

Copper

LMM (below 10 kDa) The molecular mass distribution profiles of Cu with the LMM SEC column are shown in Fig. 4a. Like in the case of the LMW UV chromatographic profiles, all the samples gave a signal in the void volume, with those from kidney and liver being the highest ones. The Cu profiles obtained for the samples analyzed were very similar in relation to the molecular mass regions in which chromatographic peaks are detected. Likewise, all the samples have a Cu-containing fraction in the void volume and in the molecular mass region from 360 to 2,126 Da. The most different chromatographic profile was obtained for the brain sample, in which a characteristic peak of Cu was detected in the molecular mass region from 7 to 10 kDa with a shoulder in the molecular mass region from 2,126 Da to 7 kDa. Some

peaks of Cu, with very low intensity, were detected in all the samples in the molecular mass region below 360 Da.

HMM (3–70 kDa) Figure 4b shows the molecular mass distribution profiles of Cu with the HMM SEC column. The Cu-containing fractions detected in the void volume of the LMM column (above 10 kDa) are present in the chromatographic profiles obtained with the HMM column within its separation range. The exception is the chromatographic profile obtained from the liver extract, which is the only one for which a Cu-containing fraction was eluted in the void volume of the HMM column (above 70 kDa). As can be observed in Fig. 4b, Cu was found to be mainly associated with molecules with molecular masses below 3 kDa and in the range from 25 to 67 kDa. A distinctive chromatographic peak was detected in the molecular mass range from 67 to 70 kDa in the lung extract.

Manganese

LMM (below 10 kDa) Typical chromatographic profiles obtained for Mn are shown in Fig. 5. All the samples

Fig. 5 Molecular size distribution patterns of Mn obtained by SEC-ICP-MS with the LMM column

analyzed have chromatographic peaks of high intensity in the molecular mass range from 360 to 2,126 Da, indicating that Mn is mainly associated with LMM compounds. However, several peaks of low intensity were detected in the void volume of this column. The extracts from heart, kidney and lung have the highest abundance of this element in the molecular mass separation range of this column. In the extract from heart only two peaks were detected, a low-abundance one in the void volume and another typical one in the molecular mass region from 360 to 2,126 Da.

HMM (3–70 kDa) The molecular size distribution patterns of Mn obtained with the HMM column are shown in Fig. S1.

Nickel

LMM (below 10 kDa) Figure 6 shows the typical molecular size distribution pattern of Ni in the extracts. Similar to Mn, this element is mainly associated with LMM compounds from 360 to 2,126 Da. The highest abundance of Ni was found in the extract of lung and the lowest in the one from liver. Other samples had very similar molecular mass distribution patterns.

HMM (3–70 kDa) The molecular size distribution patterns of Ni obtained with the HMM column are shown in Fig. S2.

Lead

LMM (below 10 kDa) The molecular size distribution pattern of Pb (Fig. 7a) is very similar to that of Ni; therefore, Pb is mainly associated with LMM compounds from 360 to 2,126 Da. The highest abundance of Pb was found in the extract from heart and the lowest was found in that from brain. In the chromatographic profile of kidney a low-abundance peak of Pb was detected in the void volume, and in that of liver two peaks were detected in the same molecular mass region.

HMM (3–70 kDa) The analysis of the extracts with the HMM SEC column (Fig. 7b) provides the molecular mass of the Pb fractions eluted in the void volume of the LMM column. This is the case for the peaks corresponding to Pb eluted in the region from 67 to 70 kDa in the chromatographic profile of kidney and in the case of liver for the two peaks corresponding to Pb eluted in the molecular mass regions from 25 to 67 kDa and from 67 to 70 kDa.

Fig. 6 Molecular size distribution patterns of Ni obtained by SEC-ICP-MS with the LMM column

Fig. 7 Molecular size distribution patterns of Pb obtained by SEC-ICP-MS with a the LMM column and b the HMM column. Numbers correspond to the standards of known molecular mass: 1 67 kDa, 2 25 kDa, 3 13.7 kDa, 4 7 kDa and 5 less than 3 kDa

Zinc

LMM (below 10 kDa) This element is mainly associated with LMM compounds in the molecular mass range from 360 to 2,160 Da as shown in Fig. 8. Several Zn-containing fractions were detected in the void volume of the LMM column but in contrast to the previously mentioned cases, the molecular mass determination with the HMM column was not successful owing to the low intensity.

HMM (3–70 kDa) The molecular size distribution patterns of Zn obtained with the HMM column are shown in Fig. S3.

Arsenic

As shown in Fig. 9, the molecular size distribution pattern of As was the most different. Only one As-containing fraction was detected in the liver extract, with a molecular mass below 360 Da.

Iron

The molecular size distribution patterns of Fe with the LMM and HMM column are shown in Fig. S4. The sensitivity with the SEC-ICP-MS coupling is not good for Fe and the noise is high as can be seen in the chromatograms.

Fig. 8 Molecular size distribution patterns of Zn obtained by SEC-ICP-MS with the LMM column

Remarkable results and further studies

From the previous data the conclusion can be drawn that most of the elements are bound to molecules in the range 360–2,126 Da in all the organs studied. There is a Cu-containing fraction (7–10 kDa) in the brain extract that is not present in any other organ of *Mus musculus*, which could be interesting for further studies. Future work will be focused on the collection of the Cu-containing fraction mentioned for purification by anion-exchange chromatography coupled with ICP-MS for final identification by organic MS. In addition, the optimized approach will be

applied to the organs of the free-living *Mus spretus* mice from Doñana National Park to find metallospecies that could be used as markers of environmental pollution.

Conclusions

The present paper reports for the first time the molecular size distribution patterns of elements in *Mus musculus* mice. In spite of *Mus musculus* being well known since a great number of proteomic and genomic studies have been performed (i.e., the genome is completely known), the

Fig. 9 Molecular size distribution patterns of As obtained by SEC-ICP-MS with the LMM column

present work is the first one focused on the study of its "metallome." The SEC-UV-ICP-MS approach is a powerful tool in these metallomics appraisals, and the fractionation profiles of the elements obtained make possible deep insight into the interactions of elements with the different organs of *Mus musculus* as well as their possible connection with the metabolic pathways in this animal. The use of ICP-MS allows multielement profiling in samples to be obtained in only one chromatographic run, which constitutes a reliable technique with high throughput. The possibility to screen many elements in a given chromatographic peak from an extract is critical since there are no errors associated with different measurements. On the other hand, biological tissues are difficult to obtain because tedious sample preparation and killing several animals to get enough sample are necessary. Therefore, ICP-MS constitutes a powerful technique to obtain the patterns of many elements in complex biological tissues and it is an excellent guide for further studies of the fraction of interest like further separations by orthogonal techniques, molecular mass-spectrometric elucidations of the metallospecies involved and so on.

Acknowledgements This work was supported by the project CTM2006-08960-C02-01 from the Ministerio de Educación y Ciencia. M.G.-F. thanks the Ministerio de Educación y Ciencia for a predoctoral scholarship.

References

- Kislinger T, Cox B, Kannan A, Chung C, Hu PZ, Ignatchenko A, Scott MS, Gramolini AO, Morris Q, Hallett MT, Rossant J, Hughes TR, Frey B, Emili A (2006) *Cell* 125:173–186
- Hoehenwarter W, Kumar NM, Wacker M, Zimny-Arndt U, Klose J, Jungblut PR (2005) *Proteomics* 5:245–257
- Oldfield CJ, Cheng Y, Cortese MS, Brown CJ, Uversky VN, Dunker AK (2005) *Biochemistry* 44:1989–2000
- Klose J (1999) *Electrophoresis* 20:643–652
- Simons MJ, Pellionisz AJ (2006) *Cerebellum* 5:27–35
- Purmann A, Toedling J, Schueler M, Carninci P, Lehrach H, Hayashizaki Y, Huber W, Sperling S (2007) *Genomics* 89:580–587
- Penkett CJ, Morris JA, Wood V, Bahler J (2006) *Nucleic Acids Res* 34:W330–W334
- Ieradi LA, Moreno S, Bolívar JP, Cappaid, A, Di Benedetto A, Cristaldi M (1998) *Environ Pollut* 102:265–268
- Ruiz-Laguna J, García-Alfonso C, Peinado J, Moreno S, Ieradi LA, Cristaldi M, López-Barea J (2001) *Biomarkers* 6:146–160
- Bonilla-Valverde D, Ruiz-Laguna J, Muñoz A, Ballesteros J, Lorenzo F, Gomez-Ariza JL, Lopez-Barea J (2004) *Toxicology* 197:123–138
- Szpunar J (2005) *Analyst* 130:442–465
- Auerbach D, Thaminy S, Hottiger MO, Stagljar I (2002) *Proteomics* 2:611–623
- Bogyo M, Hurley JH (2003) *Curr Opin Chem Biol* 7:2–4
- Hancock WS, Wu SL, Shieh P (2002) *Proteomics* 2:352–359
- Peng JM, Gygi SP (2001) *J Mass Spectrom* 36:1083–1091
- Outten CE, O'Halloran TV (2001) *Science* 292:2488–2492
- Szpunar J, Lobinski R, Prange A (2003) *Appl Spectrosc* 57:102A–112A
- Sanz-Medel A, Montes-Bayon M, Fernandez Sanchez ML (2003) *Anal Bioanal Chem* 377:236–247
- Wind M, Lehmann WD (2004) *J Anal At Spectrom* 19:20–25
- Montaser A (1998) *Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry*. Wiley, New York
- Michalke B (2004) *J Chromatogr A* 1050:69–76
- Michalke B, Schramel P (2004) *J Anal At Spectrom* 19:121–128
- Wrobel K, Kannamkumarath SS, Wrobel K, Caruso JA (2003) *Anal Bioanal Chem* 375:133–138
- Vonderheide AP, Wrobel K, Kannamkumarath SS, Hymer CB, Montes-Bayón M, de León CP, Caruso JA (2002) *J Agric Food Chem* 50:5722–5728
- Mounicou S, McSheehy S, Szpunar J, Potin-Gautier M, Lobinski R (2002) *J Anal At Spectrom* 17:15–20
- Encinar JR, Ouerdane L, Buchmann W, Tortajada J, Lobinski R, Szpunar J (2003) *Anal Chem* 75:3765–3774
- Wuilloud RG, Kannamaumarath SS, Caruso JA (2004) *Anal Bioanal Chem* 379:495–593
- Gómez-Ariza JL, Arias-Borrego A, García-Barrera T (2006) *J Chromatogr A* 1121:191–199
- Fingerová H, Koplík R (1999) *Fresenius J Anal Chem* 363:545–549
- St Remy RRD, Fernández Sánchez ML, López Sastre JB, Sanz-Medel A (2004) *J Anal At Spectrom* 19:616–622
- St Remy RRD, Fernández Sánchez ML, López Sastre JB, Sanz-Medel A (2004) *J Anal At Spectrom* 19:1104–1110